

EFFECT OF SUBSTRATE COMPOSED FROM PEA STRAW, WASTEPAPER AND WHEAT BRAN ON GROWTH AND BIOLOGICAL EFFICIENCY OF OYSTER MUSHROOM (*PLEUROTUS OSTREATU*), IN ETHIOPIA

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ABSTRACT. Mushroom production is getting more and more attention as a source of food, medicine, and means of recycling organic waste. The purpose of this paper was to report the effect of different substrates composed of waste paper, wheat bran, and pea straw (*Pisum sativum*) on growth and yield of oyster mushrooms (*Pleurotus ostreatus*). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to analyse the quantitative data collected, and pair-wise comparisons were performed using Tukey. T11 and T12 had the fastest mycelial run; 13 days each, whereas T15 had the slowest mycelial run, 25 days. T1 and T11 had the fastest primordial development (17 days), whereas T15 had the slowest primordial formation (30 days). T2 had the largest cap diameter (10 cm), the highest fresh weight (1614 g/500 g substrate), and the highest number of fruiting bodies (263); while, T15 had the lowest total biomass (565 g/ 500g substrate) and the fewest fruiting bodies (140). The stipe length was not affected by substrate composition. The maximum number of bunches (7–7.5) were from T4, T5, and T7, while the lowest (5.5) was from T12. T7 showed highest number of aborts, 205, while T15 had the fewest, 110. With 331.2% and 117%, T2 and T15 exhibited the highest and lowest biological efficiency. Pea straw mixed with varied amount waste paper and wheat bran revealed the possibility of these substrates to be used for oyster mushroom higher yield and yield-related parameters.

Keywords: Bunches, fruiting bodies, primordia, treatments, yield

INTRODUCTION

Because of their outstanding taste and restrained flavor, mushrooms have long been regarded as gourmet cuisine around the world. They are high in critical elements like as dietary fiber, minerals, and vitamins, particularly vitamin D [1]. Furthermore, mushrooms are increasingly being regarded as functional foods due to their possible health benefits. As a result, the food sector is particularly interested in edible mushrooms, both farmed and wild. *Pleurotus* (Fries) Kummer (Basidiomycota, Agaricales) is a diverse genus of mushrooms with great nutritional and medicinal value, as well as a wide range of biotechnological and environmental applications[2]. Oyster mushrooms, such as *Pleurotus ostreatus*, are rarely attacked by diseases or pests, and their cultivation does not necessitate extensive environmental control, therefore they are grown in a cheap and simple manner [3, 4]. As a cultivated mushroom, the oyster mushroom has numerous advantages, including quick mycelial development, high saprophytic colonization potential, simple and economical cultivation techniques, and a variety of species suitable for cultivation under various climatic conditions. Oyster

mushroom is also low in calories, salt, fat, and cholesterol while being high in protein, carbohydrate, fiber, vitamins, and minerals. This mushroom's nutritional characteristics make it an excellent dietary meal.

Furthermore, due to a variety of unique compounds, oyster mushroom ingestion has a good impact on overall human health [3]. Because of these characteristics, the production and consumption of this mushroom has skyrocketed in recent years, and it now ranks second only to the button mushroom. *Pleurotus* spp. have a great ability to breakdown lignin-cellulose, was also used to remove xenobiotic contaminants like pentachlorophenol (PCP), dioxin, and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) (PAHs). This shows that this mushroom could be used in innovative ways for environmental bioremediation [5; 6]. In Ethiopia, oyster mushroom cultivation on a small scale on a variety of substrates is more frequent than other mushroom species. They thrive in a wide range of temperatures and develop quickly. They also have a significant ability to colonize substrates in a short period of time and the ability to withstand increased CO₂ concentrations [7]. It is also a fast-growing mushroom that requires no composting, no casing, and is less fragile than other mushrooms. It is also marketed in a dry form. They are the apparent choice for entering into the mushroom market because they are the easiest and least expensive to grow. If not properly managed plant-derived agro-industrial waste, will causes environmental and health problems issues. Since, mushrooms can grow on a variety of raw lignocellulosic substrates and under a wide range of temperatures, this waste can be controlled through mushroom farming [4, 8] Mycelium growth, mushroom quality, and crop yields are all affected by the nature and nutrient content of the mushroom substrate.[3]. One of the limiting elements in mushroom production is the availability of a good substrate, which is required for a reasonable output of mushrooms [9]. To promote rapid mushroom growth, a suitable substrate should have nitrogen supplement and carbohydrates [10]. In most situations, the substrate lacks the nitrogen that the mushroom needs to grow properly, necessitating the addition of nitrogen to the substrate in order to improve mushroom growth [11].*P. ostreatus* requires carbon and nitrogen sources in the substratum, as well as other minerals such as S, Ca, Mg, P, K, and some lesser concentrations of minerals such as Fe, Zn, Mn, Cu, and Mo[12], with an ash content ranging from 2.5 to 15.7%.

There are a lot of agricultural wastes that are usually thrown away, but mushrooms can be successfully grown on them. Mushrooms have the ability to convert agricultural waste into nutrient-rich food, which opens up a lot of possibilities for tackling food security issues. As a result, improvements in current technical expertise are required to provide a sustainable mushroom prouction by maintaining lower-cost mushroom farming and ensuring the availability of required raw materials from a variety of sources.

Consumers currently consume roughly 5 kg of mushrooms per person per year on average As people become more aware of the health benefits of mushrooms in their diet, per capita consumption is likely to rise. To determine the biological responses of mushroom bioactive components in humans, much more research is needed[13]. Betaglucan, vitamin D, selenium, and ergothioneine may have beneficial impacts on immunological function, intestinal function, and weight control, according to reports in the literature. To achieve the desired biological response in humans, it must be determined how often, how much, and what species or mixtures of species should be

fed. Meanwhile, consumers can savour the distinct culinary qualities that mushrooms have to offer.

In central Ethiopia, agricultural waste products abound, which are typically abandoned in some locations while mushrooms can be effectively grown on it. Furthermore, Kumla *et al.*, [14] pointed out that mushrooms have the ability to convert agricultural waste into nutrient-rich food, presenting significant prospects for solving the region's food security issues. As a result, it is necessary to increase the current state of technological knowledge in order to promote (low-cost) mushroom growing, as well as the availability of required raw materials (substrates of various origins). However, there is currently no modern method of mushroom production in the central part of the country, particularly in Ambo town and its surrounding. As a result, research on oyster mushroom yield or other associated features in relation to organic substrates for growing mushrooms in the study area is nil. In Ethiopia, discarded paper and paperboard account for around 26% (or 67 million tons) of the 258 million tones of solid municipal wastes produced in 2014, and over 14% of the 136 million tons of solid municipal wastes disposed of in landfills [15]. When incinerated via traditional land fill methods paper waste, like other wastes, poses an additional hazard of toxic inks, dyes, and polymers, which could be potentially carcinogenic. The environmental and economic impact of the energy consumed by manufacturing, transporting, burying, and or reprocessing paper products is mitigated by paper recycling through mushroom production [16].

In this study the paper that was left over after being used in various university offices was evaluated for oyster mushroom production, along with pea straw and wheat bran, in order to develop substrate compositions that may have less or no use to replace the high cost of cotton seed waste for mushroom production in the country.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sources of oyster mushroom, culturing and spawn development

The oyster mushroom was received from Addis Ababa University, College of Computational and Natural Sciences, Department of Biology, Mycology Laboratory and subcultured on newly made potato dextrose agar consisting of 250g of pled and cooked potato soup, 20g of glucose, and 20 g of agar. The medium was sterilized in the autoclave for 30 minutes at 15, 121⁰C. After sterilization, the medium was distributed into pre-sterilized Petri-dishes, cooled in a safety cabinet, and inoculated with a 1cm×1cm block of fungal culture, and the inoculated media were incubated at 28±2⁰C for 15 days, with visual inspections for contamination every other day. Figure 1.1, depicts a fully grown oyster mushroom culture. The over steps followed in the mushroom production processes in this experiment is depicted by Fig 1. (1-5).

The oyster mushroom spawn was made using yellow sorghum grains as a main substrate, together with wheat bran and calcium sulphate in an 88:10:2 ratios [17]. Overnight, the sorghum grain was soaked in a suitable amount of water. The water was then drained the next day, and the broken and floating grains were washed away with the water. The grain was then thoroughly mixed with the required amount of wheat bran and calcium sulphate. The mixed spawn substrate was filled up to 75% of the way into a capped bottle, leaving room for air exchange and sterilized in the autoclave at 15, 121⁰C for 1 hour. After sterilization, the substrate was cooled in a safety cabinet before being inoculated with 20 pieces of 15-day-old fungal culture and incubated 28±2⁰C for

21 days. Every five days, it was inspected for contamination and growth, and the bottle that showed signs of contamination was removed from the incubator. Figure 1.2 depicts the ready-to-use spawn developed in this experiment.

Fig 1. The different steps followed in this experiment: 1.1. Mushroom culture, 1.2 mature ready to use. 1.2, mushroom spawn developed on sorghum grain; 1.3. A) peas straw, B) waste paper, C) wheat bran; 1.4) primordial formed on the bags that received different substrate mix ratio, 2.5 nature and quality mature mushroom fruiting bodies from the bags that received different substrate mix ratios

Substrate collection and processing

Pea straw: the pea straw was collected from a farmer's field from around the Ambo town and transported to the Microbiology Laboratory at Ambo University's Department of Biology, and the straw was reduced in size to 3 -5cm in length and stored in dry, cold places until needed. **Waste paper:** waste or used paper was collected from the Biology department's staff room, College of Natural and Computational Sciences Ambo University's and the size of paper was reduced to 2-3cm. with scissors, **Other additives:** Wheat bran was purchased from the wheat processing factory of the Guder town, calcium carbonate was collected from the microbiology laboratory department of Biology (Fig. 1.3 , Table 1).

Table1: The different substrates composition of the different treatments in these experiments.

Treatments	Pea straw (%) (g)	Waste paper(%) (g)	Wheat bran (%) (g)	Total dry substrate per bag(g)
T1	—	100% (500g)	---	500 g
T2	100% (500g)	—	---	500 g
T3	80% (400g)	20% (100g)	—	500g
T4	70% (350g)	30%(150g)	—	500g
T5	60% (300g)	40%(200g)	—	500g
T6	50%(250g)	50%(250g)	—	500g
T7	40%(200g)	60% (300g)	—	500g
T8	30% (150g)	70% (350g)	—	500g
T9	20% (100g)	80% (400g)	—	500g
T10	45% (225g)	45% (225g)	10% (50g)	500g
T11	40% (200g)	40% (200g)	20% (100g)	500g
T12	35% (175g)	35% (175g)	30% (150g)	500g
T13	30% (150g)	30% (150g)	40% (200g)	500g
T14	25% (125g)	25%(125g)	50% (250g)	500g
Positive control (T15)	Cotton seed waste (100%)			

Data analysis

All quantitative data collected were analyzed by using SPSS version 26.0 by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). All of the statistical was performed at the 0.05 significance level and was presented as mean \pm standard deviation (M \pm SD). The pair wise comparison was done and rearranged according to Tukey .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Full Mycelia colonization, primordial formation and complete production cycle of oyster mushroom grown on different substrates

As the base for the formation of fruiting bodies, vegetative growth is the first stage in the growing of mushrooms. According to Pokhrel *et al.*, [18], the proper growth of mycelium is thus a crucial component of mushroom cultivation. In this research, the variable substrate composition greatly affected the number of days needed for the oyster mushroom's mycelia colonization to be complete ($P \leq 0.05$). T11 Pea straw: waste paper: wheat bran (40:40:20) and paper waste: pea straw: wheat bran 35: 35: 30 (T12), took 13 days to colonize mycelia colonization while , T2 (Pea straw) 100 %, paper waste

:pea straw 50:50 (T6), paper waste :pea straw 30:70 (T8), paper waste : pea straw 20: 80 (T9), all took 15 days to complete mycelia colonization, and cotton seed waste (100) % took 25 days which was not comparable with the other substrates (Table 2). The findings of this study corroborates with Girmay *et al.*, [19], who reported that full mycelia colonisation required 14 to 21 days on the various substrates they investigated. According to Tesfay *et al.*, [20], mycelia colonisation took 15 to 21 days on average to complete, which show similarity with the results of our experiment. However, according to Mkhize *et al.*, [21], the time it took for mycellum to completely colonise maize stalks ranged from 30.5 days (for 8% Wheat Bran) to 56.4 days (for 20% Maize flour). Similar longer mycelia colonisation days were reported by Nasir *et al.*, [22] for saw dust 100%, which took 37 days, and maize residue 100%, which required 46 days. This discrepancy might be caused by variations in the nutrient content of the various substrate compositions, as a result of the various substrate mixing ratios used in this study. These variations may have affected by the readily availableness of various nutrients required and the capacity of the substrates to hold moisture for optimal oyster mushroom vegetative growth, leading to shorter days for mycelia colonisation.

The number of days required for primordial development following incubation varied based on the substrate compositions. T1 paper waste (100) % and T11 waste paper: pea straw: wheat bran (40: 40: 20) had the fastest primordial initiation, 17 days followed by T9 paper waste: pea straw 20: 80; T12 paper waste: pea straw: wheat bran 35:35:30 took 18 days each, while the positive control T15 cotton seed waste 100 % had the slowest primordial initiation, 30 days. The rest of the treatments, on the other hand, revealed intermediate days between the quickest and slowest primordial development (Table 2). The variation in primordial initiations could be attributed to changes in substrate compositions, as higher and lower concentrations of nutrients required for pin head formation could be optimized differently depending on the mix ratio. In comparison to substrates with low lignin and cellulose concentration, Oei [23] found that materials with high lignin and cellulose content took longer to start pinning. The results of primordial initiations in this study was comparable to those reported by Grimay *et al.*, [19], who found that pin-head development occurred swiftly in cotton seed (17 days), followed by sawdust (29 days), but required a longer period in wheat straw (32.66 days). However, the days required for primordial development in this study were significantly shorter than those reported by Nasir *et al.*, [22] who found that sawdust 100 % took the shortest time (45 days) and maize residues was taken (61 days) following spawn inoculation. Total days taken for the oyster mushroom production cycle when different substrate mix ratio was used were significantly different between treatments (Table 2). T1, Waste paper 100 % and T2, pea straw 100% both had 63 days, were the fastest complete production cycles, followed by T4, waste paper: pea straw 70 30 and T8) waste paper: pea straw 30: 70 both 66 days, and T15, cotton seed waste 100 (78 days), and T13, waste paper: pea straw: wheat bran (30: 30: 40) 77 days.

Table 2. Full *Mycelia* colonization, primordial formation and complete production cycle of mushroom grown on different substrates

Treatments	Dates for complete colonization	1st primordial formation	Date required for complete production cycle
T1	15±1.0ab	17±0.5a	63±5.1
T2	15±2.3ab	19±1.5a	63±6.8
T3	17±2.1ab	23±1.1abc	68±10.1
T4	18±2.5ab	26±1.9bcd	66±12.1
T5	20±3.1bc	28±1.2bcd	71±13.0
T6	15±3.1a b	19±1.5a	71±8.5
T7	16±0.9ab	22±2.51ab	71±11.0
T8	15±0.7ab	20±2.6ab	66±8.5
T9	15±3.0ab	18±0.91	71±10.0
T10	15±1.5ab	20±1.3a	71±3.5
T11	13±0.8a	17±1.7a	72±5.0
T12	13±0.9a	18±1.8a	69±8.0
T13	20±2.5bc	28±3.1e	77±10
T14	16±1.5ab	20±0.81a	74±3.5
T15	25±0.5c	30±1.8e	78±9.7
Sign	0.003	0.02	

Yield of Oyster mushroom per flushes, total biomass and biological efficiency

There was a significant difference in oyster mushroom yield per flush (wet weight) between treatments ($P \leq 0.05$) (Table 3). T2 had the highest fresh weight of fruiting bodies (848 g), while T15 had the lowest fresh weight of oyster mushroom (309g) in the first flush. Mondal, *et al.*, [24] reported the maximum biological yield (159.3 g) from rice straw and the minimum biological yield (36.35 g) was obtained from banana leaves and rice straw (1:1 w/w) in the first flush. Rice straw produced the highest biological yield (164.49 g) in the case of the second flush. The highest yield was obtained in T3 (761.5±7.5g) followed by 507±5 g and 317.7±3.1 g in T1 and T2, respectively [25]. The yield of oyster mushrooms differed significantly between treatments in the second harvest ($P \leq 0.05$) (Table 4). During this phase, the oyster mushroom with the highest fresh weight was T3, 483 g, while the oyster mushroom with the lowest fresh weight was T15 157 g and T12 178 g. In the third harvest, there was a significant difference in oyster mushroom yield across treatments ($P \leq 0.05$) (Table 4). The highest fresh weight of oyster mushroom was found from T5, 222g, whereas the lowest fresh weight of oyster mushroom was observed from T1, 76 g, T15, 79 g, and T13, 80 g. At the fourth harvest, there was a significant difference in oyster mushroom yield (wet weight) across treatments ($P \leq 0.05$) (Table 4). During this time, T2 98 g had the maximum fresh weight of mushroom while T15, 19 g, T1, 24, and T13, 31 had the lowest.

The total biomass of the oyster mushroom was significantly affected ($P \leq 0.05$) by the substrate composition (Table 3). In this trial the highest total biomass was recorded from T2, 1656g and the smallest from T15 565g. This result was much greater than the results reported in the literature. although it show similarities with the results reported in the literature. Maheswari *et al.*, [25] reported, the total fresh weight of the first and second flush was highest for maize cob+paddy straw (718.7 g) followed by sugarcane bagasses+paddy straw (527.8 gm), sawdust+paddy straw (459.0 g), and lowest for paddy straw(408.3gm). In this study, the highest total biomass of 1656±14.16g was

recorded from pea straw 100%(T2) , followed by pea straw: waste paper(80:20) (T3) 1369±77.5g,, pea straw: waste paper (60:40)(T5), 1312 ±101.5g;; pea straw: waste paper (50:50) (T6), 1246 ± 20.5g,, pea straw:waste paper (70:30) (T4),1263±67.41g; while the smallest total biomass was recorded from, cotton seed waste (T15) 100% 565±66.52g and waste paper (T1) 100% 691±16.25g(Table 3).

The composition of the substrate had a significant ($P\leq 0.05$) impact on biological efficiencies (BE) (Table 3). *Pleurotus ostreatus* grown on T2 had the highest BE value of 331.2 percent, followed by T3, 272 percent, and T15, 117 percent, and T1, 139 percent, respectively. The biological efficiency results in this investigation are significantly superior to those reported in the literature. Treatment-T1 (100 percent sawdust) has the highest biological efficiency (88.8%), while Treatment-T5 (100 percent maize residues) has the lowest biological efficiency (52.6%), according to Nair *et al.*, [22] The BE values ranged from 95 3 (8 percent Wheat bran) to 158 11 (14 percent Maize flour). 14 percent Maize flour (158 11) and 12 percent Wheat bran (156 6) had the greatest BE, followed by 14 percent Wheat bran (148 3). The lowest BE was found in the 8% Wheat bran (95 30) and 2% Maize flour (109 17) samples. When comparing each supplement level from 2% to 20% with the control (0%), the 12 percent Wheat bran (156 6), 14 percent Wheat bran (148 3), and 14 percent Maize flour (158 11) were considerably higher than the non-supplemented maize stalk (control) with a biological efficiency of 119. 4 percent [21]. Mushroom bioconversion efficiency on different substrates mixtures having 45:45 and 90:10 ww main materials and additive wheat bran for three consecutive flushes: mixtures of cotton waste and coffee pulp their bioconversion efficiency was 79%, followed by 76% of cotton waste and Tef straw mixture, 63% of coffee pulp and tef straw mixture, 61% of cotton waste and wood chips mixture, 58% of coffee pulp and wood chips mixture, 52% of wood chips and tef straw mixture [26]. The mushroom produced from rice straw + wheat straw substrates (RS+WS) followed by (RS) had higher biological efficiency (BE) than the other substrates (126.7 and 110.8 percent, respectively). In general, substrates that produced better yields also produced higher BE values. The lowest mushroom yield, as well as the lowest BE, was found in the substrate 100 percent (WH) followed by (SD). Variances in oyster mushroom production and BE were due to differences in the physical and chemical composition of substrate formulations, such as cellulose/lignin ratio and mineral content, pH, and EC of substrate, in particular C/N ratio. Low substrate nitrogen was one of the parameters influencing overall yield and BE when compared to other substrates [27]. The chemical and nutritional composition of substrates, on the other hand, affects the yield and quality of oyster mushrooms [28, 29].

Table 3. Yield of Oyster Mushroom per flushes, total biomass and biological efficiency grown on different substrate compositions per flushes

Treatments	1 st flush	2 nd flush	3 rd flush	4 th flush	Total biomass	Biological efficiency
T1	401±8.0 ^{gh}	294±7.5 ^{fg}	76±4.0 ^d	24±6.0 ^{hi}	691±16.25 ^{hi}	139±4.5 ^h
T2	848±9.0 ^a	456±3.5 ^{ab}	204±20.5 ^{abc}	98±8.0 ^a	1656±14.16 ^a	331.2±20.4 ^a
T3	685±45.50 ^{abc}	483±25 ^a	194±33.0 ^{bcd}	66±6.0 ^{bc}	1369±77.55 ^b	272±12.1 ^b
T4	634±30 ^{bcdef}	366±12.6 ^{abcd}	196±25.5 ^{abc}	65±2.0 ^{bc}	1263±67.41 ^{bc}	252±10.5 ^b
T5	623±10.3 ^{bcdef}	401±18.5 ^{abc}	222±19.0 ^a	63±3.0 ^{bc}	1312±101.53 ^{bc}	262±15.1 ^b
T6	643±15.5 ^{bcd}	404±22.6 ^{bcde}	117±11.0 ^{cd}	51±2.0 ^{def}	1264±20.5 ^{cde}	233±13.5 ^c
T7	525±7.3 ^{cdefg}	298±6.6 ^{cdef}	131±14.9 ^{bcd}	49±1.0 ^{ef}	1002±106 ^{efg}	201±16.0 ^{de}
T8	589±79.0 ^{bcdef}	280±23.7 ^{def}	97±12.5 ^d	41±1.5 ^{fg}	1005±15.52 ^{efg}	201±13.0 ^{de}

T9	470±30.0 ^{fgh}	295±3.0 ^{cdef}	106±2.5 ^d	44±2.1 ^f	915±29.5 ^{fg}	183±6.51 ^{fg}
T10	636±18.0 ^{bcd}	247±24.6 ^{efg}	114±11.5 ^d	71±3.0 ^{bc}	1066±53.05 ^{def}	214±8.5 ^d
T11	691±23.0 ^a	367±17.5 ^{abcd}	95±23.8 ^d	60±5.3 ^{cd}	1208±15.53 ^{bcd}	250±9.5 ^c
T12	567±18.9 ^{bcd}	178±16.5 ^{def}	108±13.7 ^d	59±2.9 ^{cde}	1014±63.53 ^{efg}	203±10.0 ^{de}
T13	478±15.5 ^{efg}	248±19.2 ^{efg}	80±4.0 ^d	31±3.5 ^{gh}	833±78.51 ^{gh}	170±5.1 ^g
T14	506±26.9 ^{defg}	248±29 ^{def}	124±17.5 ^{cd}	41±1.1 ^{fg}	947±51.50 ^{fg}	191±4.9 ^{ef}
T15	309±23.0 ^h	157±17.2 ^g	79±0.5 ^d	19±2.0 ⁱ	565±66.52 ⁱ	117±3.8 ⁱ
Sign	0.000				0.000	0.000

Number of matures, aborts, bunches, pilus diameter and stipe length of oyster mushroom grown on different substrates

Among substrate types, the number of ripe mushrooms gathered differed considerably ($P \leq 0.05$) (Table 4). T3, 263 had the most matures, followed by T2, 254, T3, 245, and T4, 244, and T15, 141 had the least. This result was at par with the results reported by Sitaula *et al.* [30]. According to these authors, the substrate of T2 produced (108) fruiting bodies on average, followed by T1 (80) and T3 (20). The maximum number of effective fruiting bodies 74.25 was recorded on sawdust substrate and the minimum, was 12.75 on banana leaves [24].

The number of pinheads that were aborted differed considerably ($P \leq 0.05$) between substrate types (Table 4). In this study, the maximum number of aborted pin heads was found in T7, 205, followed by T3, 200, while the lowest number of aborted pin heads was found in T15, 110. Mondal *et al.* [24] reported the highest (7.798 cm) pileus diameter on sawdust substrate and the lowest (4.13 cm) on banana leaves and rice straw (1:3) ratio. According to the study reported by Abera *et al.*, [17], different substrates had different effects on the yield-related parameter of oyster mushrooms. The largest cap-diameters and stipe length of oyster mushrooms grown on these substrates were recorded on the bags received 30:30:40% wheat straw: waste paper and cotton seed waste and 40:40:20% the same substrate composition, while the smallest cap diameter of 6.23cm was measured from wheat straw 25%: waste paper 25% and cotton seed waste 50%. The smallest stipe length was measured from 20:20:60% wheat straw: waste paper: cotton seed waste. In this study the stipe length of the oyster mushroom grown on different substrates showed slight variation from 3.5 -2.00 cm.

The number of bunches produced by oyster mushrooms growing on various substrate compositions varied considerably ($P \leq 0.05$) (Table 4). T5, 7.5, produced the most bunches in this sample, whereas T12, 5.5, produced the fewest number of bunches. The maximum number of bunches per bag (7.66 bunches) were obtained by using 100 g spawn per kg on substrate dry weight basis. It was followed by 80 and 90 g (6.37 bunches), 70 g (5.33 bunches), 60 g (5.00 bunches), 50 g (3.33 bunches), 40 g (3.00 bunches). The spawn @ 30, 20 and 10 g gave 2.00 bunches [31].

The largest mean cap diameter of *P. ostreatus* was found from T2 (10cm), followed by T10 and T14 (9cm), while the smallest mean cap diameter was found in T1 and T15 (5cm). The highest (7.90±2.66 cm) and the lowest (5.40±1.57 cm) mean pileus diameter were noted on T3 and T5, respectively. Significant difference was observed between T3 and T4. Besides, pileus diameter among fushes was not significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) different except in the second and third fushes of T2 and T3 [20].

Similarly, the stipe length of the samples varied significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) depending on the treatment, ranging from 3 cm to 4 cm cm (Table 7). T10 had the longest stipe length

(4cm), while T1, T5, T6, T8, and T9 had the shortest stipe length (3cm)[29]. Mushroom grown on mixture of cotton waste and coffee pulp had the highest stipe diameter (2.75 cm). The lowest stipe and piles diameter of the cultivated oyster mushroom was recorded in the mixture of wood chips + tef straw [26].

Table 4. Number of matures, aborts, bunches, cap diameter and stipe length of oyster mushroom grown on different substrates

Treatments	Number of matures	Number of aborts	Number of bunches	Cap diameter	Stipe length
T1	181±4.0 ^h	154±2.0 ^{cdef}	6±0.5	7±0.5	3±1.0
T2	254±5.0 ^{ab}	190±12.0 ^{ab}	6±2.0	10±2.0	3.5±0.5
T3	263±6.0 ^a	200±10.0 ^{ad}	6±3.0	8±1.0	3.5±0.5
T4	244±8.9 ^{bc}	195±5.0 ^{ab}	7±3.8	8±0.5	3.5±1.0
T5	245±6.0 ^{bc}	195±4.5 ^{abc}	7.5±2.65	8±2.0	3±1.5
T6	233±3.0 ^{de}	198±8.0 ^{ab}	6±1.15	8±1.2	3±1.0
T7	236±1.0 ^{cd}	205±1.0 ^a	7±2.1	8±1.0	4±4.0
T8	208±8.0 ^f	168±2.5 ^{bcd}	6±3.0	8±2.0	3±1.6
T9	181±4.0 ^h	140±5.0 ^{defg}	6±0.6	8±1.0	3±1.0
T10	195±1.0 ^g	165±4.0 ^{bcde}	6±1.5	9±2.0	4±2.0
T11	223±3.0 ^e	190±3.0 ^{ab}	6±2.1	8±1.5	3.5±2.0
T12	206±4.0 ^f	170±8.0 ^{bcd}	5.5±2.1	8±2.0	3.5±0.5
T13	161±1.0 ⁱ	120±5.0 ^{fg}	6±0.6	8±2.5	3.5±1.0
T14	191±4.0 ^{gh}	132±2.0 ^{efg}	6±3.0	9±2.9	3.5±0.9
T15	140±5.0 ^j	110±5.0 ^g	6±2.6	7±2.0	3.5±1.0
Sign	0.000	0.000			

CONCLUSIONS

Finding or developing substrates or substrates mix ratio that will produce higher yields and higher-quality mushrooms is crucial as mushroom production technology becomes more significant for solid organic waste recycling, boosting nutrition, and medicinal applications. Accordingly, it was investigated how wastepaper, pea straw, and wheat bran could be used as a substrate for growing oyster mushrooms. It was found that the composition of the substrate had an impact on the yield, yield-related parameters, total biomass, and biological efficiency. This suggests that substituting these substrate and substrate compositions for cotton seed waste could boost oyster mushroom yield and nutrient content while lowering production costs.

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